

8T – Freezing Time

"Some great new ideas are required." Richard Feynman.

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main features of the 8T it is possible to expand on the idea of time as presented in the 8T thesis. In particular it is possible to predict that at extremum energies, given by the fourth term on the main equation of the 8T, it will be possible to freeze time, or to make it vanish. Author argues for this result using several different ideas.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M , given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^K \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (2. A1)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matrix tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We have presented the spin classification in the 8T thesis, page seventeen, while using the prime critical line:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $N = 2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

Up to this point was introduction, reader is probably familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. **From here** on out, we have a completely **new paper**. The subject of this paper would be the fourth term of the main equation. The question in hand would be its physical meaning, what does it mean $\partial g / \partial t = 0$ as we required for a stationary manifold. In previous papers author considered it as a gate to space that is flat, the Ricci flow space which is in between two manifolds and is accessible in extremum energies, high or low, so in that idea the term $\partial g / \partial t = 0$ referred to curvature in the context of energy. This term is also considering areas of maximal curvature such as black holes and galaxies, as presented above. If we consider black holes as an area of extremum curvature and correlate it to the term, $\partial g / \partial t = 0$ it means that time vanishes in a black hole; it is the same at all for an observer inside a critical range, and only pass for observer outside a critical range. When derived the primordial coupling series in March 21, very soon later the author correlated the direction of the series to the direction of time. That is in page thirty of the 8T thesis.

$$1 > \frac{3}{30} > \frac{5}{128} > \frac{7}{850} \dots$$

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Therefore, in other sense, we can take ratios of net variation and state in the primorial the following term apply:

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \neq 0$$

From gluons, clustering triplets of arbitrary variations we move to heavy weak interaction Bosons with mass due to the additional element inserted, than to photons and so on. The direction of the series is the direction of time, but it does not answer what time really is. Of course that the real answer is that the author does not know. In the 8T thesis, the author considered **time** as a **parameter** that is intimately **connected to the variation** of the net element which create a difference in what there is, different amount of clustering leading to different objects, bigger clusters. In that sense we have $\partial g / \partial t \neq 0$. Since black holes swallow matter, but also omit radiation, the amount of curvature they contain is not varying and can be described by , $\partial g / \partial t = 0$ which also implies that the arrow of time freeze or that time does not pass.

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} + \delta g + (-\delta g(H)) = 0$$

Therefore, time, despite being so elusive can be correlated to two different features, the set of prime net variations that differ from one another, in particular the jumps from coupling to coupling. The second is that time is correlated to energies that are not extremum $\partial g / \partial t \neq 0$ and in extremum energies , $\partial g / \partial t = 0$ time does not pass, or at least time does not seem as passing. An observer generating energies at the level of , $\partial g / \partial t = 0$ in a mathematical sense is to create a maximal curve, the maximal curve does not vary with time, as it is a maximal point and so to an outside observer time is standing still. We can make a prediction:

(1) An observer able to generate energies at the magnitude $\partial g / \partial t = 0$ will freeze time, at the area of generation for an unknown radius.

By freezing, one means that the observer will measure a space that is standing still.

References

[1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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